

Thermodynamics of Electrolyte Solutions : An Emf Study of the Activity Coefficients of NaCl in NaCl + Ba(NO₃)₂ + H₂O System

E. YADAIHAH and J. ANANTHASWAMY*

Department of Chemistry, Osmania University, Hyderabad-500 007

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Electromotive force measurements have been carried out on the system NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O at *I* = 0.1, 0.25 and 0.5 mol kg⁻¹ and at 25, 35 and 45° using a cell consisting of sodium ion-selective electrode and an Ag/AgCl electrode. The data are analysed using the Pitzer and Harned equations. The osmotic coefficients, activity coefficients of Ba(NO₃)₂ and excess free energies of the aqueous mixtures have been estimated at 25°. The solubilities at 20° are interpreted using the Pitzer binary and ternary interaction parameters.

The thermodynamic properties of aqueous electrolyte solutions are useful in several fields. However, the ternary mixtures of aqueous alkali metal halides with alkaline earth metal nitrates have not received much attention. Xu *et al.*¹ estimated the activity coefficients of NaCl in the systems NaCl–Mg(NO₃)₂–H₂O, NaCl–Ca(NO₃)₂–H₂O, NaCl–Sr(NO₃)₂–H₂O at 25°. However, we could not find any work in the literature on the activity coefficients of the system NaCl–Br(NO₃)₂–H₂O. Hence, in the present study the mean ionic activity coefficients of aqueous NaCl solutions in the system NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O were estimated at 25, 35 and 45° and at total ionic strengths of 0.1, 0.25 and 0.5 mol kg⁻¹ using emf studies, in continuation of our earlier work on the activity of NaCl in aqueous mixed electrolyte solutions²⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

The emfs of sodium ion-selective electrode vs Ag/AgCl electrode in NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O system are given by the equation,

$$E = E_0 + k \log(a_{\text{Na}^+} a_{\text{Cl}^-} + K a_{\text{Ba}^{2+}}^{1/2} a_{\text{Cl}^-}) \quad (1)$$

where, $k = (RT/F) \ln 10$ which is the Nernst slope and E_0 is the emf due to the sodium chloride solution at unit activity. The selectivity coefficient (*K*) values were in the range 10⁻⁵ to 10⁻⁴ at the ionic strengths studied, and hence $K a_{\text{Ba}^{2+}}^{1/2} a_{\text{Cl}^-}$ term in eqn. (1) could be neglected. As $a_{\text{Na}^+} = (m_A + 2m_B)\gamma_+$ and $a_{\text{Cl}^-} = m_A \gamma_-$, eqn. (1) could be rearranged as

$$\gamma_{\pm}^2 = [1/(m_{\text{Na}^+} m_{\text{Cl}^-})] 10^{(E-E_0)/k} \quad (2)$$

Hence, the mean activity coefficients of NaCl could be determined by substituting the emfs of the cell with NaCl + Ba(NO₃)₂ mixture, i.e. *E* in eqn. (2). The experimental mean ionic activity coefficients of NaCl in aqueous NaCl + Ba(NO₃)₂ system were determined at *I* = 0.1, 0.25 and 0.5 mol kg⁻¹ and at 25, 35 and 45° and are listed in Table 1, at different values of the ionic strength fractions (y_B) of Ba(NO₃)₂, where $y_B = 3m_B/(m_A + 3m_B)$. The plots of $\log \gamma_{\text{NaCl}}$ vs y_B at all the ionic strengths studied are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Mean activity coefficients of NaCl in NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O system.

TABLE 1—MEAN ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF NaCl IN NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O SYSTEM

<i>I</i> = 0.1		<i>I</i> = 0.25		<i>I</i> = 0.5	
y_B	$-\log \gamma$	y_B	$-\log \gamma$	y_B	$-\log \gamma$
Temp. = 25° :					
0.099 1	0.109 6	0.094 9	0.143 5	0.092 6	0.168 3
0.180 3	0.110 6	0.173 4	0.144 8	0.169 4	0.169 3
0.248 1	0.110 6	0.239 3	0.145 1	0.234 3	0.170 0
0.305 6	0.111 9	0.295 5	0.145 7	0.289 8	0.170 8
0.354 8	0.112 1	0.344 0	0.146 1	0.337 7	0.172 2
0.397 6	0.112 7	0.386 2	0.146 9	0.379 6	0.172 1
0.435 0	0.112 5	0.423 4	0.146 9	0.416 6	0.172 9
0.457 2	0.112 1	0.456 2	0.147 7	0.449 3	0.173 6
0.468 1	0.112 3	0.474 4	0.147 4	0.478 6	0.173 9
0.483 4	0.112 1	0.485 6	0.148 2	0.488 0	0.173 7
0.497 5	0.112 6	0.500 7	0.148 0	0.514 4	0.174 8
0.512 8	0.113 4	0.530 1	0.147 9	0.543 7	0.175 2
0.546 1	0.113 1	0.563 2	0.148 4	0.576 6	0.175 3
0.584 0	0.113 7	0.600 7	0.149 3	0.613 7	0.175 8
0.627 5	0.113 1	0.643 5	0.149 2	0.656 0	0.177 0

Table-1 (contd.)

0.678 0	0.114 1	0.692 9	0.149 7	0.704 4	0.177 1
0.737 3	0.114 1	0.750 5	0.150 2	0.760 6	0.178 2
0.808 1	0.115 4	0.818 6	0.150 8	0.826 6	0.179 8
0.893 9	0.116 4	0.900 2	0.153 1	0.905 1	0.179 9
Temp. = 35°:					
0.097 9	0.110 3	0.093 8	0.140 4	0.093 1	0.165 8
0.178 4	0.110 6	0.171 6	0.141 4	0.170 4	0.166 5
0.245 7	0.111 8	0.237 0	0.142 2	0.235 6	0.167 1
0.302 8	0.112 4	0.292 9	0.142 4	0.291 2	0.167 1
0.351 8	0.113 0	0.341 2	0.142 5	0.339 3	0.167 7
0.394 4	0.113 0	0.383 2	0.142 9	0.381 3	0.168 0
0.431 8	0.114 1	0.420 3	0.143 5	0.418 3	0.168 3
0.455 7	0.114 6	0.453 1	0.143 1	0.451 1	0.168 5
0.464 8	0.114 2	0.482 4	0.143 3	0.480 4	0.168 5
0.481 9	0.114 9	0.490 7	0.143 8	0.488 0	0.168 6
0.494 2	0.114 1	0.517 0	0.144 0	0.514 4	0.168 6
0.511 4	0.114 7	0.546 3	0.144 3	0.543 7	0.169 5
0.544 6	0.115 5	0.579 2	0.144 1	0.576 6	0.169 8
0.582 5	0.116 0	0.616 2	0.144 8	0.613 7	0.170 2
0.626 1	0.116 0	0.658 3	0.145 0	0.656 0	0.169 9
0.676 7	0.117 3	0.706 6	0.145 4	0.704 4	0.170 4
0.736 2	0.116 9	0.762 6	0.145 8	0.760 6	0.170 7
0.807 2	0.117 4	0.828 1	0.146 1	0.826 6	0.171 1
0.893 3	0.117 2	0.906 0	0.146 9	0.905 1	0.172 0
Temp. = 45°:					
0.101 9	0.109 6	0.102 6	0.141 1	0.100 6	0.168 6
0.185 0	0.110 2	0.186 1	0.142 7	0.182 9	0.169 9
0.254 0	0.111 2	0.255 3	0.143 1	0.251 3	0.170 1
0.312 2	0.112 0	0.313 7	0.144 0	0.309 2	0.170 2
0.362 0	0.112 9	0.363 6	0.145 1	0.358 8	0.169 6
0.405 1	0.113 6	0.406 8	0.145 1	0.401 7	0.170 6
0.442 7	0.114 6	0.444 5	0.146 2	0.439 3	0.170 3
0.471 2	0.113 6	0.477 6	0.145 7	0.469 0	0.171 2
0.475 9	0.113 9	0.489 9	0.146 4	0.472 4	0.170 9
0.497 5	0.115 8	0.507 0	0.146 8	0.495 3	0.171 4
0.505 3	0.114 8	0.516 3	0.147 1	0.501 8	0.170 6
0.526 9	0.114 7	0.545 6	0.147 0	0.524 8	0.170 8
0.560 0	0.115 1	0.578 4	0.147 5	0.557 9	0.171 2
0.597 6	0.116 6	0.615 5	0.148 1	0.595 5	0.170 8
0.640 6	0.117 0	0.657 7	0.148 5	0.638 6	0.171 3
0.690 2	0.117 1	0.706 0	0.149 3	0.688 3	0.171 4
0.748 1	0.117 8	0.762 0	0.149 8	0.746 5	0.171 6
0.816 7	0.119 8	0.827 7	0.150 2	0.815 4	0.171 4
0.899 1	0.119 7	0.905 7	0.151 6	0.898 3	0.172 6

The activity coefficient data at each ionic strength and all the temperatures studied were fitted to the Harned equation⁵,

$$\log \gamma_A = \log \gamma_A^0 - \alpha_{AB} \nu_B \quad (3)$$

where, γ_A^0 is the activity coefficient of pure NaCl solution. The resulting Harned coefficient (α_{AB}) values are listed in Table 2. The activity coefficient data at 25° were further analysed using the Pitzer equations^{6,7},

$$\ln \gamma_M = Z_M^2 F + \sum_a m_a (2B_{Ma} + ZC_{Ma}) + \sum_c m_c (2\theta_{Mc} + \sum_a m_a \Psi_{Mca}) + \sum_{a<a'} m_a m_{a'} \Psi_{Maa'} + |Z_M| \sum_c \sum_a m_c m_a C_{ca} \quad (4)$$

$$\ln \gamma_X = Z_X^2 F + \sum_c m_c (2B_{cX} + ZC_{cX}) + \sum_a m_a (2\theta_{Xa} + \sum_c m_c \Psi_{cXa}) + \sum_{c<c'} \sum_c m_c m_{c'} \Psi_{cc'X} + |Z_X| \sum_c \sum_a m_c m_a C_{ca} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{where, } F = -A_\phi \left[\frac{\sqrt{I}}{1 + b\sqrt{I}} + \frac{2}{b} \ln(1 + bI^{1/2}) \right] + \sum_c \sum_a m_c m_a B'_{ca} + \sum_{c<c'} \sum_c m_c m_{c'} \theta_{cc'} + \sum_{a<a'} \sum_a m_a m_{a'} \theta_{aa'} \quad (6)$$

$$B_{ca} = \beta_{ca}^0 + \beta_{ca}^1 g(\alpha I^{1/2})$$

$$B'_{ca} = \beta_{ca}^1 g'(\alpha I^{1/2})/I$$

$$\theta_{ij} = {}^S\theta_{ij} + {}^E\theta_{ij}(I) \quad (7)$$

where all other symbols have their usual significance.

TABLE 2 – HARNED COEFFICIENTS OF NaCl FOR NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O SYSTEM

<i>I</i> mol kg ⁻¹	log γ_A^0	α_{AB}	RMSD × 10 ⁴
Temp. = 25°			
0.1	-0.109 4	-0.006 9	4.185
0.25	-0.143 6	-0.008 9	5.048
0.5	-0.166 7	-0.015 1	2.873
Temp. = 35°			
0.1	-0.108 9	-0.011 2	5.397
0.25	-0.139 9	-0.007 8	2.093
0.5	-0.164 8	-0.008 0	2.480
Temp. = 45°			
0.1	-0.107 7	-0.014 0	4.752
0.25	-0.139 9	-0.013 1	2.696
0.5	-0.169 3	-0.003 0	3.897

The Pitzer coefficients at 25° for the pure salts are taken from the literature^{3,7,8} and listed below :

$$\beta_{NaCl}^0 = 0.075373, \beta_{NaCl}^1 = 0.277031, C_{NaCl}^\phi = 0.001407$$

$$\beta_{Ba(NO_3)_2}^0 = -0.0430, \beta_{Ba(NO_3)_2}^1 = 1.07, C_{Ba(NO_3)_2}^\phi = 0$$

$$\beta_{BaCl_2}^0 = 0.29073, \beta_{BaCl_2}^1 = 1.24998, C_{BaCl_2}^\phi = -0.03046$$

$$\beta_{NaNO_3}^0 = 0.0068, \beta_{NaNO_3}^1 = 0.1783, C_{NaNO_3}^\phi = -0.00072$$

The values of the Pitzer mixing parameters are given below^{4,9} :

$${}^S\theta_{NaBa} = 0.0670; \quad {}^S\theta_{ClNO_3} = 0.0164;$$

$$\Psi_{\text{NaBaCl}} = -0.0120; \quad \Psi_{\text{NaBaNO}_3} = 0;$$

$$\Psi_{\text{ClNO}_3\text{Na}} = -0.0076; \quad \Psi_{\text{ClNO}_3\text{Ba}} = -0.017$$

These Pitzer parameters could fit well the experimental activity coefficient data at 25° with RMSD = 4.28 × 10⁻³ at I = 0.1, RMSD = 4.69 × 10⁻³ at I = 0.25 and RMSD = 6.36 × 10⁻³ at I = 0.5. Next, these Pitzer parameters were used to calculate the osmotic coefficients of the NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O system and the results are listed in Table 3. The activity coefficients of Ba(NO₃)₂ in this system at 25° were also calculated and the values are given in Table 4.

The excess free energies (Δ_mG^E) of the mixture were calculated using the equation¹⁰,

$$\Delta_m G^E = Y_A [\ln(\gamma_A/\gamma_A^\lambda) + (\phi_A - \phi_m)] + Y_B [\ln(\gamma_B/\gamma_B^\lambda) + (\phi_B - \phi_m)] \quad (8)$$

$$Y_A = \nu_A \gamma_A m_A RT; \quad Y_B = \nu_B \gamma_B m_B RT \quad (9)$$

where, φ_A and φ_B are osmotic coefficients of the pure components at the same ionic strength as the mixture and φ is the osmotic coefficient of the mixture, and all other symbols have their usual significance. The resulting values are listed in Table 5. Thus, these θ and Ψ values along with other Pitzer parameters are able to represent well, the thermodynamic data of the system at 25°.

TABLE 3—OSMOTIC COEFFICIENTS IN NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O SYSTEM

Temp. = 25°			
y _B	I = 0.1	I = 0.25	I = 0.5
1.0	0.843 9	0.794 3	0.748 8
0.9	0.860 0	0.818 5	0.783 0
0.8	0.873 5	0.838 5	0.810 9
0.7	0.884 8	0.855 2	0.834 0
0.6	0.894 6	0.869 4	0.853 3
0.5	0.903 0	0.881 4	0.869 6
0.4	0.910 4	0.891 9	0.883 4
0.3	0.916 9	0.901 0	0.895 3
0.2	0.922 7	0.908 9	0.905 5
0.1	0.927 9	0.915 9	0.914 3
0.0	0.932 5	0.922 1	0.922 0

The solubilities of NaCl in the mixture NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O at 20° are listed in literature¹¹. The activity coefficients of NaCl in these mixtures could be calculated from the solubility data using the relation, ΔG_s^o = –RT ln (m_{Na} m_{Cl} γ_±²). The ΔG_s^o value (–2107.55 cal mol⁻¹) of NaCl at 20° is taken from the literature¹¹. For this system at an ionic strength of 10.65 m, the solubility data gives γ_{NaCl} = 0.898 at 20°. At the same ionic strength, the Pitzer equation predicts a value of 0.869 at 25° which is in reasonable agreement with that at 20° value (0.898) calculated using the solubility data. Thus, Pitzer equation with the appropriate parameters listed above, adequately represents

the thermodynamic data of the system upto very high ionic strengths as well.

TABLE 4—MEAN ACTIVITY COEFFICIENTS OF Ba(NO₃)₂ IN NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O SYSTEM

Temp. = 25°						
y _B	I = 0.1		I = 0.25		I = 0.5	
	y _B	–log γ	y _B	–log γ	y _B	–log γ
0	0	0.233 0	0	0.311 9	0	0.374 7
0.099 1	0.099 1	0.230 2	0.094 9	0.308 7	0.092 6	0.371 6
0.180 3	0.180 3	0.228 4	0.173 4	0.306 6	0.169 4	0.370 2
0.248 1	0.248 1	0.227 4	0.239 3	0.305 6	0.234 3	0.369 7
0.305 6	0.305 6	0.226 6	0.295 5	0.305 0	0.289 8	0.370 0
0.354 8	0.354 8	0.226 1	0.344 0	0.305 0	0.377 7	0.370 5
0.397 6	0.397 6	0.226 1	0.386 2	0.305 0	0.379 6	0.371 4
0.435 0	0.435 0	0.225 9	0.423 4	0.305 3	0.416 6	0.372 3
0.457 2	0.457 2	0.225 9	0.456 2	0.305 6	0.449 3	0.373 5
0.468 1	0.468 1	0.226 0	0.474 4	0.305 8	0.478 6	0.374 6
0.483 4	0.483 4	0.226 0	0.485 6	0.306 1	0.488 0	0.374 9
0.497 5	0.497 5	0.226 1	0.500 7	0.306 4	0.514 4	0.376 0
0.512 8	0.512 8	0.226 1	0.530 1	0.307 0	0.543 7	0.377 5
0.546 1	0.546 1	0.226 4	0.563 2	0.307 7	0.576 6	0.379 3
0.584 0	0.584 0	0.226 7	0.600 7	0.308 8	0.613 7	0.381 5
0.627 5	0.627 5	0.227 2	0.643 5	0.310 2	0.656 0	0.384 4
0.678 0	0.678 0	0.228 0	0.692 9	0.312 1	0.704 4	0.388 0
0.737 3	0.737 3	0.229 2	0.750 5	0.314 6	0.760 6	0.392 8
0.808 1	0.808 1	0.237 0	0.818 6	0.318 3	0.826 6	0.398 9
0.893 9	0.893 9	0.233 4	0.900 2	0.323 2	0.905 1	0.407 3

TABLE 5—EXCESS FREE ENERGY (J kg⁻¹ OF WATER) FOR NaCl–Ba(NO₃)₂–H₂O SYSTEM

Temp. = 25°			
y _B	I = 0.1	I = 0.25	I = 0.5
0.1	–0.061 3	–0.096 2	0.173 3
0.2	–0.108 9	–0.169 8	0.317 8
0.3	–0.142 9	–0.221 2	0.430 1
0.4	–0.163 2	–0.251 0	0.506 2
0.5	–0.169 9	–0.259 5	0.542 7

Experimental

The cell consisted of Na-ion selective electrode (Elico, ENA) and an Ag/AgCl electrode¹² immersed in a mixture of aqueous NaCl and Ba(NO₃)₂ solution placed in a double-walled glass vessel whose temperature was maintained within ± 0.01°. The cell arrangement was

The analytical grade NaCl (Merck) and Ba(NO₃)₂ (s.d. chem.) were used after purification and drying. The stock solutions of NaCl were standardised volumetrically. AgNO₃ and Ba(NO₃)₂ solutions were standardised volumetrically using EDTA. Deionised, double-distilled

water was used for preparation of stock solutions. All solutions were prepared by weight. The electrodes were connected to a high-impedance ($\approx 10^{12} \Omega$) unit gain amplifier. The output of this amplifier was measured by a Keithley DMM 191 electrometer/multimeter. The accuracy of the emf measurements was upto 0.01 mV. The electrodes were first standardised at each of the ionic strengths studied. At every ionic strength a set of four experiments was carried out. In the first set, NaCl solution was taken in a double-walled glass cell and conductance water was added in successive aliquots. The potential difference was noted after each addition and equilibration. This set of results was used to calibrate the electrodes. In the second set, NaCl solution was taken in the cell and $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution was added in successive aliquots. The third set was made by starting with $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution and adding NaCl solution in aliquots. The overlapping portion between the second and third sets was used to test the reproducibility and accuracy of the measurements. In the fourth set, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution was taken in the cell and the emfs were noted after adding conductance water in aliquots. This set of results was used to calculate the selectivity coefficient of Na-ion-selective electrode towards Ba^{2+} ion in $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ solution. The solubility of $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ in water is very low (0.391 *m* at 25°). Therefore, the experiments could be carried out upto a maximum ionic strength of 0.5 only, in order to avoid the precipitation of salts after the addition of NaCl solution.

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